

PHARMACOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF DRUGS USED IN BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

Davurova Laylo

Assistant, Department of Clinical Pharmacology, Samarkand State Medical University

Dovurov Ulug'bek

Student of group 503, Faculty of Pharmacy, Samarkand State Medical University

Abstract: Allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis (ABPA) is a hypersensitivity reaction to *Aspergillus* species (usually *A. fumigatus*) that occurs primarily in patients with asthma and, less commonly, cystic fibrosis. Immune reactions to *Aspergillus* antigens lead to airway obstruction and, if untreated, to bronchiectasis and pulmonary fibrosis. The signs and symptoms are consistent with those of bronchial asthma, with productive cough, sometimes fever, and anorexia. To confirm the diagnosis, skin testing for *Aspergillus* is performed and levels of IgE, circulating precipitins, and antibodies to *A. fumigatus* are determined. In refractory cases, treatment is with corticosteroids and itraconazole.

Keywords: Pathophysiology, Clinical manifestations, Diagnostics, Treatment, Allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis.

INTRODUCTION

Allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis develops when the airways of a patient with asthma or cystic fibrosis are colonized by *Aspergillus* species (fungi found in soil).

For unknown reasons, colonization in these patients leads to the production of antibodies (IgE and IgG) and cellular immune responses (type I, III, and IV hypersensitivity reactions) to *Aspergillus* antigens, which leads to frequent, recurrent exacerbations of asthma. Over time, the immune responses, combined with the direct toxic effects of the fungus, lead to airway damage with dilation and, ultimately, the development of bronchiectasis and fibrosis. Histologically, the disease is characterized by airway obstruction with mucus, eosinophilic pneumonia, infiltration of alveolar septa with plasma and mononuclear cells, and an increase in the number of bronchiolar mucous glands and cuboidal cells.

Rarely, other fungi, such as *Penicillium*, *Candida*, *Curvularia*, *Helminthosporium*, and *Drechslera*, cause a similar syndrome called allergic bronchopulmonary mycosis; in this case, bronchial asthma or cystic fibrosis are not present.

Aspergillus is present in the lumen of the airways, but invasion does not occur. Thus, it must be distinguished from ABPA

Invasive aspergillosis affecting immunocompromised patients

Aspergillomas, which are clusters of *Aspergillus*, have been identified in patients with lung cavities or cysts.

Aspergillus pneumonia is rare and occurs in patients who have been taking low doses of prednisone for a long time (for example, in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease).

Despite clear differences, similar syndromes were observed.

RESEARCH METHODS AND APPROACHES

Symptoms resemble those of an exacerbation of bronchial asthma or pulmonary cystic fibrosis; in addition, there is a cough with dirty green or brown sputum, and sometimes hemoptysis. Fever, headache, and anorexia are common systemic signs of severe illness. Symptoms are manifestations of airway obstruction, characteristic of which are wheezing and prolonged exhalation, which are also observed during exacerbations of bronchial asthma.

Diagnosics

- a. History of bronchial asthma
- b. Chest X-ray or high-resolution computed tomography scan
- c. Aspergillus antigen skin test
- d. Aspergillus Aspergillus precipitins in blood
- e. Positive sputum culture for Aspergillus species (or less commonly other fungi)
- f. IgE level
- g. Eosinophil content in the blood

In patients with asthma or cystic fibrosis, the presence of recurrent exacerbations of the disease, the presence of migratory or fixed infiltrates on chest radiography (often due to atelectasis due to the presence of mucus plug and bronchial obstruction), bronchiectasis on imaging and a positive culture result for *A. fumigatus*, or marked peripheral blood eosinophilia should be suspected.

Allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis

Several diagnostic criteria have been proposed (see table Diagnostic criteria for allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis), but not all criteria are assessed in almost every case.

When the diagnosis is suspected, the most appropriate first step is a skin prick test with Aspergillus antigen, but serological testing using the Aspergillus precipitation test may be a more practical initial test. An immediate allergic reaction to the test with clear skin signs (papules, redness, and rash) is a reason to measure serum IgE levels and antibodies to Aspergillus (precipitins), since up to 25% of patients with asthma without allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis have a positive skin test. An IgE level > 1000 ng/ml (> 417 IU/ml) and a positive precipitation indicate the diagnosis, which should be confirmed by measuring Aspergillus-specific immunoglobulins (up to 10% of healthy patients have circulating precipitins). If ABPA is suspected, the diagnosis is confirmed by the concentration of *A. fumigatus*-specific IgG and IgE antibodies, if it is at least twice as high as in patients without ABPA.

Sputum and bronchoscopic Aspergillus cultures have low sensitivity and specificity for the diagnosis of ABPA and are not included as diagnostic criteria.

In cases where test results are conflicting, such as when serum IgE levels are elevated but *A. fumigatus*-specific immunoglobulins are not detected, the test should be repeated and the patient followed over time to confirm or rule out the diagnosis.

Asthma

Abbreviations: **AKT** - Protein kinase B, **AP-1** - Activator protein 1, **Ca²⁺** - Calcium, **CaM** - Calmodulin, **cAMP** - Cyclic adenosine monophosphate, **CD** - Cluster of Differentiation, **GαQ** - Gq protein alpha subunit, **GPCR** - G protein-coupled receptor, **IL** - Interleukin, **IP3** - Inositol 1,4,5-Triphosphate, **KCl** - Potassium chloride, **MIP-2B** - Macrophage inflammatory protein-2-beta, **MLCK** - Myosin light chain kinase, **MLCP** - Myosin light chain phosphatase, **MMP** - Matrix metalloproteinase, **MUC5AC** - Mucin 5AC, **NFAT** - Nuclear factor of activated T cells, **PDE4** - Phosphodiesterase-4, **PI3K** - Phosphoinositide 3-kinase, **PIP2** - Phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate, **PLCβ** - Phospholipase C beta, **RhoA** - Ras Homolog Family Member A, **ROCK** - Rho-associated coiled-coil protein kinase, **SHP-1** - Src homology 2 domain-containing protein tyrosine phosphatase 1, **SPDEF** - SAM pointed domain containing ETS transcription factor, **STAT6** - Signal transducer and activator of transcription 6, **TLR** - Toll-like receptor, **YKL-40** - Chitinase 3-like protein 1.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Patients with stage I disease should receive 0.5–0.75 mg/kg of prednisone once daily for 2–4 weeks, then taper over 4–6 months. Chest radiography, blood eosinophil counts, and IgE levels should be performed

quarterly to monitor progress toward improvement, defined as the detection of infiltrates, a $\geq 50\%$ reduction in eosinophil counts, and a $\geq 33\%$ reduction in IgE levels. Patients who have progressed to stage II disease require only annual monitoring.

Stage II patients who relapse (stage III) receive another course of prednisone. Stage I or III patients who fail prednisone therapy (stage IV) are candidates for antifungal agents. Itraconazole 200 mg twice daily for 16 months is used as a replacement for prednisone. In addition, pooled data identify biologics such as omalizumab as steroid-sparing agents. Treatment of symptoms and complications in stage V patients is usually supportive.

Itraconazole therapy requires monitoring of blood drug concentrations, liver enzymes, triglycerides, and potassium levels.

Stages of allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis

All patients should be treated for the underlying disease, such as bronchial asthma or cystic fibrosis. In addition, patients on long-term corticosteroid therapy should be carefully monitored for complications such as cataracts, diabetes mellitus, and osteoporosis; such patients may be given prophylactic treatment to prevent bone demineralization and *Pneumocystis jirovecii* pulmonary infection.

Allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis (ABPA) is considered if a patient with asthma or cystic fibrosis has frequent exacerbations of unknown cause, if there are migratory or low-resolution infiltrates on chest radiography, if there is evidence of bronchiectasis on CT scans, persistent blood eosinophilia, or if sputum cultures reveal *Aspergillus*.

Drugs of these classes (see table. Drug therapy for chronic bronchial asthma) are used by inhalation, taken orally or administered subcutaneously or intravenously; Inhalation drugs are available in the form of aerosols and powders. Spraying aerosols with a spacer or holding chamber facilitates the delivery of the drug to the respiratory tract, rather than to the pharynx; Patients are advised to wash and dry their spacers after each use to prevent bacterial contamination. In addition, the use of aerosol forms requires synchronization between pressing the inhaler (delivering the drug) and inhalation. Powder forms reduce the need for synchronization, since the drug is delivered only when the patient inhales fully with sufficient force.

Beta-agonists

Beta-2 adrenergic receptor agonists and beta-agonists relax bronchial smooth muscle, inhibit mast cell degranulation and histamine release, reduce capillary leak into the airways, and enhance mucus clearance. Beta-2 agonists can be short-acting, long-acting, and ultra-long-acting (see tables: Drug Therapy for Chronic Bronchial Asthma and Drug Therapy for Exacerbations of Asthma).

Short-acting beta-2 agonists (e.g., albuterol), administered as needed, 2 inhalations every 4 hours, are the drugs of choice for the relief of acute bronchospasm and for the prevention of exercise-induced asthma. They should not be used alone for the long-term treatment of chronic asthma. They begin to act within minutes and remain active for 6 to 8 hours, depending on the drug. The most common side effects of inhaled beta-agonists include tachycardia and tremor. Their severity depends on the dose of the drug. Minor hypokalemia has been observed rarely. The use of levalbuterol (a solution containing the R-isomer of albuterol) theoretically reduces adverse effects, but its efficacy and safety for long-term use have not been proven. Oral beta-agonists have more pronounced systemic effects and should generally be avoided.

Long-acting beta-agonists (e.g. salmeterol) have a duration of action of up to 12 hours. They are prescribed for moderate to severe asthma, but not as monotherapy. The drugs have a synergistic effect with inhaled corticosteroids and allow for a reduction in their dose.

Ultra-long-acting beta-agonists (e.g. indacaterol) last up to 24 hours and are used to treat moderate to severe asthma and are never used as monotherapy. The drugs have a synergistic effect with inhaled corticosteroids, allowing their dosage to be reduced.

The safety of long-term regular use of beta-agonists has been demonstrated in numerous randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses, including a large international safety study that led the Food and Drug Administration to remove the black box warning (1). Because the safety and efficacy of long-acting beta-agonists have been demonstrated only when used in combination with inhaled corticosteroids, all long- and ultra-long-acting beta-agonists should be used only in combination with inhaled corticosteroids. When asthma is not adequately controlled with other asthma controllers (e.g., low- to medium-dose inhaled corticosteroids) or when the severity of the disease clearly requires additional support. Daily use or reduction in the effect of short-acting beta-agonists or use of ≥ 1 canister per month indicates inadequate control and the need to initiate or increase other therapies.

Anticholinergic drugs (muscarinic receptor antagonists)

Anticholinergics, which are competitive antagonists of muscarinic (M3) receptors, relax bronchial smooth muscle. Ipratropium has an additive effect when used with short-acting beta-2 agonists. Side effects include dilated pupils, blurred vision, and dry mouth. Tiotropium bromide (delivered via a micronized inhaler, 1.25 mcg/actuation) is an anticholinergic drug with 24-hour action that can be prescribed to patients with asthma. Clinical trials of tiotropium added to inhaled corticosteroids or a combination of inhaled long-acting beta-2 agonists and corticosteroids in patients with asthma have shown improvements in lung function and reduced asthma exacerbations.

Corticosteroids

Corticosteroids inhibit airway inflammation, downregulate beta-receptors, and inhibit cytokine production and adhesion protein activation. They block the late response (but not the early response) to inhaled allergens. Routes of administration: oral, intravenous, and inhalation. Early administration of systemic glucocorticoids during an acute exacerbation stops it, reduces the need for hospitalization, prevents relapses, and accelerates recovery. Oral and intravenous routes of administration are equally effective.

Inhaled corticosteroids have no effect on acute attacks, but are indicated for long-term suppression, control, and relief of inflammation and symptoms. They significantly reduce the need for maintenance therapy with oral corticosteroids. Local side effects of inhaled corticosteroids include dysphonia and oral candidiasis, which can be avoided or reduced by using a spacer and/or rinsing the mouth with water after inhalation. Systemic effects are dose-dependent and can occur either orally or by inhalation, with inhalation occurring primarily at doses >800 mcg/day. Side effects of corticosteroids include suppression of the pituitary-adrenal axis, osteoporosis, cataracts, skin atrophy, hyperphagia, and a tendency to bruise. It is not clear whether inhaled corticosteroids cause growth retardation in children. Most children treated with inhaled corticosteroids eventually reach their estimated adult height. Reactivation of latent tuberculosis may occur with the use of systemic corticosteroids.

Mast cell stabilizers

Mast cell stabilizers inhibit the release of histamine from mast cells, reduce airway hyperresponsiveness, and block the early and late phases of the allergic reaction. They are used by inhalation as a prophylactic

measure for patients with exercise-induced asthma or allergic asthma. Mast cell stabilizers are ineffective once symptoms have occurred. They are the safest of all asthma medications, but they are also the least effective.

Leukotriene modifiers

Leukotriene modifiers are given orally and can be used for long-term control and symptom prevention in patients with moderate to severe chronic asthma. The main adverse effect is elevation of liver enzymes (due to zileuton). However, occasionally patients develop a clinical syndrome resembling eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis.

Methylxanthines

Methylxanthines relax bronchial smooth muscle (possibly by inhibiting phosphodiesterase) and improve myocardial and diaphragm contractility (mechanism unknown). Methylxanthines inhibit intracellular calcium release, reduce capillary permeability in the respiratory mucosa, and inhibit the late phase of the allergic reaction. They reduce eosinophil infiltration into the bronchial mucosa and T-cell infiltration into the epithelium.

Methylxanthine theophylline is used as an adjunct to beta-2-agonists for long-term control. Extended-release theophylline helps control nocturnal asthma. Theophylline is not used because of its greater risk of side effects and drug interactions than other medications. Side effects include headache, vomiting, irregular heartbeat, seizures, and worsening of gastroesophageal reflux (caused by decreased pressure in the lower esophageal sphincter).

Methylxanthines have a narrow therapeutic index; the metabolism and excretion of methylxanthines are affected by many drugs (any drugs metabolized by cytochrome P450 enzymes, such as macrolides) and diseases (such as fever, liver disease, heart failure). Serum theophylline levels should be monitored periodically and maintained between 5 and 15 µg/mL (28 and 83 µmol/L).

Immunomodulators

Immunomodulators include omalizumab, an anti-IgE antibody, 3 IL-5 antibodies (benralizumab, mepolizumab, reslizumab), and a monoclonal antibody that blocks IL-4 and IL-13 signaling by blocking the IL-4 alpha receptor (dupilumab). Immunomodulators are used to treat severe asthma, which is usually resistant to a combination of gradual asthma therapy, which includes high doses of inhaled corticosteroids with long-acting beta2-adrenergic receptor agonists, and is primarily characterized by an increase in biomarkers of allergic inflammation (serum IgE, blood eosinophil count). The choice of drug should be individualized for each patient's clinical scenario, taking into account the route of administration, frequency, cost, and concomitant atopy. For example, dupilumab may be considered in a patient with atopic dermatitis and asthma, as it is also used in patients with atopic dermatitis.

Omalizumab is indicated for patients with severe allergic asthma with high IgE levels. The drug reduces the number of asthma exacerbations, the need for corticosteroids, and symptoms. The dosage is determined using a dosage calculation table based on the patient's body weight and IgE levels. The drug is injected subcutaneously every 2-4 weeks.

Mepolizumab, reslizumab, and benralizumab are monoclonal antibodies developed for use in patients with eosinophilic asthma and block IL-5 or its receptor, IL-5R. IL-5 is a cytokine that activates eosinophilic inflammation in the airways.

Mepolizumab reduces the frequency of exacerbations, improves asthma symptoms, and reduces the need for systemic corticosteroid therapy in patients with asthma. Based on clinical trial data, efficacy is achieved with an absolute blood eosinophil count $> 150/\text{mL}$ ($0.15 \times 10^9 /\text{L}$). In patients requiring chronic systemic corticosteroid therapy, the threshold for efficacy is unclear due to the suppressive effect of corticosteroids on blood eosinophils, but mepolizumab reduces or eliminates the need for systemic corticosteroid therapy. Mepolizumab is administered subcutaneously at 100 mg every 4 weeks.

Reslizumab also reduces the frequency of exacerbations and improves asthma symptoms. In clinical studies, the total eosinophil count in patients was approximately $400/\mu\text{L}$ ($0.4 \times 10^9 /\text{L}$). The number of eosinophils that was reached in patients receiving long-term systemic corticosteroids was unknown. Reslizumab is administered intravenously at a dose of 3 mg/kg over 20 to 50 minutes every 4 weeks.

Benralizumab is a monoclonal antibody that binds to the IL-5 receptor. It is indicated for the adjunctive treatment of severe asthma in patients 12 years of age and older with an eosinophilic asthma phenotype. It is indicated to reduce the frequency of exacerbations and reduce and/or eliminate the need for oral corticosteroids. The recommended dose is 30 mg subcutaneously once every 4 weeks for 3 doses, followed by 30 mg every 8 weeks.

Dupilumab is a monoclonal antibody that blocks the IL-4R-alpha subunit, thereby simultaneously inhibiting IL-4 and IL-13 signaling. It is indicated for the adjunctive treatment of moderate to severe asthma in patients 12 years of age and older with eosinophilic phenotype or oral corticosteroid-dependent asthma. The recommended dose is an initial dose of 400 mg subcutaneously followed by 200 mg every week or 600 mg subcutaneously followed by 300 mg every two weeks. A higher dose is recommended for patients who require concomitant oral corticosteroids, with the goal of tapering and discontinuing systemic corticosteroids.

Clinicians prescribing one of these immunomodulators should be prepared to recognize and treat anaphylactic or allergic hypersensitivity reactions. Anaphylaxis may occur after any dose of dupilumab, benralizumab, omalizumab, or reslizumab, even if previous doses were well tolerated. Allergic hypersensitivity reactions have also been reported with mepolizumab. Mepolizumab has been associated

with herpes zoster infection, so vaccination against herpes zoster virus is recommended before starting therapy unless contraindicated.

Other drugs

Other medications are used to treat asthma in rare cases and under specific circumstances. Magnesium supplements are used in the intensive care unit but are not recommended for maintenance.

Immunotherapy is indicated for patients with allergies who have a good history and positive allergy tests. Immunotherapy is more effective in children than in adults. If symptoms do not improve significantly within 24 months, therapy is discontinued. If symptoms improve, therapy is continued for ≥ 3 years or longer, but the optimal duration is unknown.

Other immunosuppressive drugs are sometimes prescribed to reduce the dependence on high doses of oral corticosteroids, but they increase the risk of toxicity. Low doses of methotrexate (5-15 mg orally or intramuscularly once a week) may cause a small increase in FEV1 and a small decrease in daily oral corticosteroid use. Gold preparations and cyclosporine are also somewhat effective, but their toxicity and the need for appropriate monitoring limit their use.

Other treatments for chronic asthma include nebulized lidocaine, nebulized heparin, colchicine, and high-dose intravenous immunoglobulin. Evidence supporting the effectiveness of any of these options is limited and their benefits have not been proven, so none of them are currently recommended for routine clinical use.

List of used literature:

1. U.S. Food and Drug Administration: FDA Drug Safety Communication: FDA review finds no risk of serious asthma outcomes with long-acting beta-agonists (LABAs) used in combination with inhaled corticosteroids (ICS). Updated December 20, 2017. Accessed January 21, 2022.
2. Закирова Б. И. и др. Пищевая аллергия у детей //Достижения науки и образования. – 2021. – №. 4 (76). – С. 65-66.
3. Abilkasimovna K. G., Shavkatovich G. J., Shokirovna D. L. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ КЛИНИКО–ЭТИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВНЕБОЛЬНИЧНОЙ ПНЕВМОНИИ У ДЕТЕЙ С МИОКАРДИТАМИ //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 3.
4. Лим М. В., Давурова Л. Ш. УСОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ИНСТРУМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ МЕТОДОВ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ПРИ ВНЕБОЛЬНИЧНОЙ ПНЕВМОНИИ У ДЕТЕЙ С МИОКАРДИТАМИ //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2022. – №. 3 (159). – С. 35-39.
5. Rustamovich, A. I., Negmatovich, T. K., & Fazliddinovich, S. D. (2022). БОЛАЛИКДАН БОШ МИЯ ФАЛАЖИ ФОНИДА РИНОСИНУСИТИ БОР БЕМОРЛАРДА БУРУН БЎШЛИГИ МУКОЦИЛИАР ТРАНСПОРТИ НАЗОРАТИ ТЎҒРИСИДАГИ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР (адабиётлар шарҳи). JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 7(2).
6. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Шамсиев, Д. Ф. (2021). Эффективность применения местной антибиотикотерапии в лечении параназального синусита у детей с церебральным параличом. In НАУКА И ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ: СОХРАНЯЯ ПРОШЛОЕ, СОЗДАЁМ БУДУЩЕЕ (pp. 336-338).
7. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Шамсиев, Д. Ф. (2021). Болаликдан бош мия фалажи билан болалардаги ўтқир ва сурункали параназал синуситларни даволашда мукорегуляр дори воситасини самарадорлигини ўрганиш. Т [a_XW [i [S US S_^[Ûe YfcS^, 58.
8. Siddikov, O., Daminova, L., Abdurakhmonov, I., Nuralieva, R., & Khaydarov, M. OPTIMIZATION OF THE USE OF ANTIBACTERIAL DRUGS DURING THE EXACERBATION OF CHRONIC

- OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE. Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, 32, 2.
9. Andryev S. et al. Experience with the use of memantine in the treatment of cognitive disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 282-288.
 10. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 29-35.
 11. Asanova R. et al. Features of the treatment of patients with mental disorders and cardiovascular pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 545-550.
 12. Begbudiyevev M. et al. Integration of psychiatric care into primary care //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 551-557.
 13. Bo'Riyev B. et al. Features of clinical and psychopathological examination of young children //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 558-563.
 14. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 36-41.
 15. Ivanovich U. A. et al. Efficacy and tolerance of pharmacotherapy with antidepressants in non-psychotic depressions in combination with chronic brain ischemia //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 409-414.
 16. Nikolaevich R. A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 898-903.
 17. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 413-419.
 18. Pachulia Y. et al. Assessment of the effect of psychopathic disorders on the dynamics of withdrawal syndrome in synthetic cannabinoid addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 240-244.
 19. Pachulia Y. et al. Neurobiological indicators of clinical status and prognosis of therapeutic response in patients with paroxysmal schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 385-391.
 20. Pogosov A. et al. Multidisciplinary approach to the rehabilitation of patients with somatized personality development //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 245-251.
 21. Pogosov A. et al. Rational choice of pharmacotherapy for senile dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 230-235.
 22. Pogosov S. et al. Gnostic disorders and their compensation in neuropsychological syndrome of vascular cognitive disorders in old age //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 258-264.
 23. Pogosov S. et al. Prevention of adolescent drug abuse and prevention of yatrogenia during prophylaxis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 392-397.
 24. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 186-191.
 25. Prostyakova N. et al. Changes in the postpsychotic period after acute polymorphic disorder //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 356-360.

26. Prostyakova N. et al. Issues of professional ethics in the treatment and management of patients with late dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 158-165.
27. Prostyakova N. et al. Sadness and loss reactions as a risk of forming a relationship together //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 252-257.
28. Тураев, Х. Н. (2021). Абдурахмонов Илхом Рустамович Влияние будесонида на качество жизни пациентов с бронхиальным обструктивным синдромом. Вопросы науки и образования, 7, 132.
29. Абдурахманов, И., Шамсиев, Д., & Олимжонова, Ф. (2021). Изучение эффективности мукорегулярных препаратов в лечении острого и хронического параназального синусита при детском церебральном параличе. Журнал стоматологии и краниофациальных исследований, 2(2), 18-21.
30. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Шамсиев, Д. Ф. (2023). БОШ МИЯ ФАЛАЖИ ФОНИДАГИ ПАРАНАЗАЛ СИНУСИТЛАРНИ ДАВОЛАШДА ЎЗИГА ХОС ЁНДАШИШ. MedUnion, 2(1), 14-26.
31. Орипов, Р. А., Абдурахмонов, И. Р., Ахмедов, Ш. К., & Тураев, Х. Н. (2021). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ АНТИОКСИДАНТНЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ НЕЙРОДЕРМИТА.
32. Ахмедов, Ш. К., Тураев, Х. Н., Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Орипов, Р. А. (2021). НЕКОТОРЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТАКТИКИ ПРОДУКТИВНОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ КРАПИВНИЦЫ.
33. Абдурахмонов, И. Р. (2021). Исследование мукоцилиарной транспортной функции слизистой оболочки полости носа у больных с параназальным синуситом на фоне детского церебрального паралича. In Актуальные аспекты медицинской деятельности (pp. 256-259).
34. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Тураев, Х. Н. (2022). ОПЫТ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ СИНУПРЕТА С АНТИБАКТЕРИАЛЬНЫМИ ПРЕПАРАТАМИ В КОМПЛЕКСНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ РИНОСИНУСИТОВ У БОЛЬНЫХ ДЕТСКИМ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНЫМ ПАРАЛИЧОМ. Достижения науки и образования, 2 (82)), 88-92.
35. Abdurakhmanov, I., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS IN CHILDREN. Science and innovation, 2(D10), 164-168.
36. Ванг Ю. и др. Способ оценки повреждения миокарда в условиях перфузии изолированного сердца по методу Лангендорфа //Фармация и фармакология. – 2024. – Т. 12. – №. 2. – С. 105-116.
37. Ванг, Ю., Смолярчук, Е. А., Кудлай, Д. А., Щекин, В. С., Завадич, К. А., Сологова, С. С., ... & Самородов, А. В. (2024). Способ оценки повреждения миокарда в условиях перфузии изолированного сердца по методу Лангендорфа. Фармация и фармакология, 12(2), 105-116.
38. Abdurahmonov , I. (2024). MECHANISM OF ACTION OF ANTIBACTERIAL DRUGS IN COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA IN YOUNG CHILDREN. Modern Science and Research, 3(11), 353–362. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/48040>
39. Abdurakhmonov, I. R., & Shamsiev, D. F. (2021). The effectiveness of topical antibiotic therapy in the treatment of paranasal sinusitis in children with cerebral palsy. Science and education: preserving the past, creating the future, 336-338.